

A NEW APPROACH TO FINANCE THE GUARANTEED HEALTHCARE PACKAGE

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Introduction

The basic social obligation of the government is to provide universal health coverage (UHC) for the community, irrespective of its residency and social status. However, despite the view that financing of healthcare should be based on per capita expenses for the community, the factual policy does not consider this. Such approach intimidates a constitutional and other rights of individuals to get fair and equitable healthcare, in every region.

Study objective

To evaluate the need for resource optimization basing on healthcare financing and guaranteed package data analysis, in the regional (tuman, town) level.

Materials and methods

A review of national regulations regarding management of regional (tuman, town) healthcare organizations with a retrospective and expert-based analysis of the healthcare resource allocation at Tashkent region's (viloyat) tumans and towns.

Results

Regional (tuman, town) healthcare departments are providing guaranteed services for the cost of government budget. To evaluate the policy of healthcare financing, we analyzed per capita allocation of budgetary resources on Tashkent region's tuman and town healthcare facilities, during period of 2023-2024. Considering the size of community and total sum of budget resources assigned, per capita government health expenditure in 2024 were following in: Tashkent tuman -393,7 thsnd. sums (2023 - 368,2 thsnd. sums), Ohangaron tuman - 446,1 thsnd. (2023 - 350,4 thsnd.), Kibray tuman - 455,9 thsnd. (2023 - 496,6 thsnd.), Chinoz tuman - 534,1 thsnd. (2023 - 427,8 thsnd.), Urta Chirchik tuman - 221,8 thsnd, with no beds (2023 - 229,9 thsnd.).

Discussion

The per capita government (budget) health expenditures standards are provided on Cabinet of Ministers decree №217 (since Sep 28, 2005). The results of our analysis demonstrate that practical per capita expenditures do not conform those requirements. Such policy contributes inequality in primary healthcare access, in Tashkent region. This fact, in turn, violate the issues of Constitution and State Law "On protecting the health of citizens" that require equity for all in term of health services quality and volume, limiting the financial access to healthcare guaranteed by the government.

Conclusions

1. It is very critical issue to accept clear standards for guaranteed per capita government health expenditures and suggest them to the healthcare providers.

2. It is important to stop the practice of parallel purchasing (payment for) the guaranteed package of care both directly from the healthcare provider and through the regional health department, which is formally pooling all government resources to purchase the healthcare.
3. Irrespective their status of ownership, all healthcare providers should be formally contracted to purchase the healthcare concerning the accepted per capita standards to provide the guaranteed service delivery for all.